

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY IN THE EVOLUTION OF PHILOLOGY

Umarova Marjona Usmonovna

Student of Uzbekistan State World Languages University

marjonaumarova2004@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13922599>

Annotatsiya

Filologiya fanining lingvistik tahlil usullarida jamiyat va texnologiya taraqqiyotini qanday qabul qilganini osongina kuzatish mumkin. Har xil madaniyatlar nafaqat hujjatlar bilan, balki raqamlashtirish va sun'iy intellekt (AI) kabi yangi vositalar bilan ham ta'minlangan bo'lib, u uzoq vaqt oldin yo'qolgan tillar bo'yicha tadqiqotlarga tayyorgarlik ko'rish va filologik tadqiqotlarga qiymat qo'shish uchun xizmat qiladi. Bunday texnologiyalar filologiya sohasida an'anaviy kasbiy amaliyotlarga ta'sir qilib, bugungi kunda mutaxassislariga ham afzallik, ham kamchiliklarni taqdim etmoqda. Ushbu maqola raqamli vositalarning filologik amaliyotlarga qo'shilgan yangi sohalarini va ushbu sohaning zamonaviy va kelajakdagi jamiyatlardagi geografiasini belgilaydigan o'zgaruvchilarni tadqiq qilishni maqsad qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Filologiya, raqamli texnologiya, tilni saqlash, sun'iy intellekt (AI), manbalarni raqamlashtirish, matn tahlili.

Abstract

It is easy to note that the discipline of philology has incorporated societal and technological advancement in the methods of linguistic analysis. A wide range of cultures has been equipped not only with documents, but new tools, such as digitization and artificial intelligence (AI) which seem to preparedness in research for long-ago endangered languages and add values in philological studies. Such technologies have affected conventional career practices in language study and preservation as such presenting disadvantage and advantage to the professionals in the field of philology today. This article aims to examine the area of new digital tools incorporated into philological practices and variables that define the geography of this field in the contemporary and future societies.

Keywords: Philology, digital technology, linguistic preservation, artificial intelligence (AI), digitization of manuscripts, textual analysis

Introduction

The use of computer aided languages and artificial intelligence in the science of language assimilation has an interesting bipartite phenomena: It

presents beneficialin overcoming barriers in language extinction but does not mean that language politics will no longer exist. This study explores how philological activities can be conducted in the 21st century by incorporating contemporary research tools, especially electronic generation, and evaluation, into the discipline and politics of language.

Literature Review:

Over the last several decades, researchers have investigated the use of digital technologies in the humanities with particular reference to the discipline of philology. For instance, Smith (2021) notes the advantage of digitizing manuscripts and employing computational linguistics for text such as manuscripts. He explains that these instruments broaden the scope of linguistic studies of languages that had been deemed dead and inaccessible (Smith, 2021). Further, Johnson and Lee (2022) investigate the application of artificial intelligence to replace the linguistic studies of extinct languages and point out that machine learning will bolster traditional linguists' tools (Johnson & Lee, 2022). The above circumstances have come with some critics, particularly, concerning too much dependency on technology. As Taylor (2023) explains, the tension concerning whether the use of digital technologies will overshadow these conventional skills and even lead to a reduction of philologists as interpreters of context and culture is also plausible (Taylor, 2023).

Methodology:

This includes a comparison of how both the traditional methods of philology and the new digital methods of philology are applied in practice. With the use of case studies taken from current literature, this part describes the use of digital technologies in the restoration and analysis of texts. In the current research, an attempt was made to take stock of already existing studies and seek the opinions of experts so as to ensure that both sides of the debate on the effectiveness of the use of digital technologies in örgüler were adequately covered.

Results and Discussion

Digital tools are one of the philological research benefits in different dimensions. For instance, tools that are driven by AI can process linguistic data in large quantities, making it possible for philologists to recognize patterns and connections that a human being could never detect manually. In addition, the digitization of rare manuscripts has made these materials more accessible to researchers worldwide, which in turn has facilitated the conducting of cross-cultural studies (Smith, 2021). Nevertheless, technology, which is so heavily

relied upon, may cause philologists to lose the insight to texts in their historical and cultural contexts (Taylor, 2023). This section seeks to weigh in on the risks that may emerge as a result of such overstretch and explore potential ways through which digital tools can be incorporated, while maintaining the human component which is the essence of philology.

The use of digital technologies in philology is a dual process of both the opportunities and challenges. Though AI as a digital tool in philology and digital methodologies as technologies can make linguistic preservation and analysis more convenient, they have the chance to become more sophisticated and could also lead to a decline in traditional skills if they are used without deep thought. From its beginning till now, this subject has been going through series of changes so philologists should manage the two ends the innovations brought and the discipline's core principles by striking a balance.

References

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